

Explainability Metrics for Object Detection Models

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Abstract. Object detection models based on deep learning achieve state-of-the-art accuracy in many applications, but their predictions are difficult to interpret. Existing explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) techniques for computer vision mostly focus on image classification, and their direct extension to object detection is non-trivial, as detectors must explain both *what* was detected (class) and *where* it was detected (bounding box). In this paper, we revisit perturbation-based saliency methods for object detection, with a particular focus on D-RISE, a popular model-agnostic technique. We highlight practical limitations of D-RISE, particularly the absence of a detector-specific importance score aligned with detection performance. We then propose a novel detection-loss based explainability score that quantifies the importance of each image region through the deterioration of the detector’s loss under random masking. The proposed score jointly accounts for classification confidence and localisation quality, and it is normalised to be in $[0, 1]$, providing an interpretable per-pixel importance measure. The proposed score is evaluated on three datasets covering industrial and general-object detection scenarios. In addition to qualitative visualization, we report object-level explainability statistics and deletion-based fidelity analysis to assess the alignment between highlighted regions and detection confidence. The results indicate that the proposed Δ -based scoring method produces consistent and interpretable saliency maps that are directly linked to changes in detection loss. Overall, the proposed approach establishes a principled link between visual explanations and detection performance, and paves the way for robust, quantitative comparison of XAI methods for object detection.

Keywords: Explainable artificial intelligence · Object detection · Saliency maps · D-RISE · Detection loss · YOLO.

1 Introduction

Deep learning based object detectors such as the YOLO family [13] have become the standard in many industrial and safety-critical applications (e.g., [4, 12]), ranging from surveillance and autonomous driving to quality control in manufacturing. These models simultaneously localize and classify multiple objects in an image, achieving high mean average precision (mAP) on benchmarks such as COCO [6]. Despite their success, they remain not fully transparent: the decision to place a bounding box at a specific location with a given class label is indeed not directly interpretable for practitioners or domain experts.

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) aims to improve transparency, trust, and debugging ability of black-box models. In computer vision, most XAI research has focused on image classification, where gradient-based methods (e.g., Grad-CAM [16], Layer-wise Relevance Propagation [2], Integrated Gradients [11, 17]) and perturbation-based methods (e.g., LIME [14], SHAP [7], RISE [9]) produce saliency maps that highlight pixels influencing a given prediction. However, these methods do not directly address the dual nature of object detection, where explanations have to take into account both *class* and *localization*.

Recent works proposed explainability methods specifically adapted to object detection, such as perturbation-based approaches like D-RISE [10] and BODEM [8], as well as surrogate-based frameworks such as SODEx [15]. D-RISE and BODEM generate per-detection saliency maps by applying random masking strategies and aggregating detection confidence responses, while SODEx builds a surrogate classifier for a specific detection and explains it through a model-agnostic classification explainer.

These approaches provide practitioners with valuable visual insights, but still present some challenges:

- the absence of a numeric explainability score aligned with detection performance;
- sensitivity to masking parameters and upsampling strategies;
- lack of robustness analysis and standardised evaluation;
- limited connection between saliency and detection accuracy or error.

In this paper, we address some of these challenges by introducing a detection-loss based saliency score for object detectors. Instead of relying on heuristic similarity measures between base and masked detections, we quantify the importance of a region by the amount in which its masking increases the detection loss. This provides a natural link between explainability and model performance, allowing to define a normalised, detector-specific importance value in $[0, 1]$ for each pixel.

Contributions. Our main contributions can be summarised as it follows. (i) we review perturbation-based explainability methods for object detection, with emphasis on D-RISE and its limitations;(ii) we propose a novel detection-loss based explainability score that jointly captures classification confidence and localisation quality;(iii) we define a normalisation scheme that turns raw loss differences into a comparable saliency scale between 0 and 1; and(iv) we describe an

evaluation protocol for object-detection saliency maps including sanity checks, localization metrics (e.g., pointing game) and fidelity metrics (deletion and insertion), and we empirically evaluate the proposed method using deletion-based analysis. The proposed framework is model-agnostic by design and does not rely on internal gradients, making it scalable to different detection architectures.

2 Related Work

2.1 XAI Methods in Computer Vision

XAI techniques for computer vision can be broadly divided into gradient-based and perturbation-based methods.

Gradient-based methods exploit gradients or relevance scores from internal layers of a neural network to assign importance to input pixels. Examples include Grad-CAM [16], Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) [2], and Integrated Gradients [11, 17]. These methods are typically model-dependent and require access to internal activations and gradients.

Perturbation-based methods modify the input and observe changes in model predictions. To estimate the relevance of a region, they occlude or mask it and measure how much the prediction changes. Examples include LIME [14], SHAP [7], and RISE [9]. These methods are often model-agnostic and therefore attractive in settings where internal details of the detector are not available.

While both families have been successfully applied to classification, their extension to object detection introduces additional challenges: explanations must be associated to specific detections, and both classification and localisation must be taken into account.

2.2 Explainability for Object Detection

Recent XAI methods for object detection tailor perturbation-based ideas to the detection setting. Table 1 summarises three representative approaches.

Method	Type	Main characteristics
D-RISE [10]	Perturbation	Per-detection saliency using random masks; similarity based on IoU, class score, and objectness.
SODEx [15]	Perturbation	Adapts classification explainers (e.g., LIME) to object detection via surrogate modeling.
BODEM [8]	Perturbation	Explains detections using hierarchical masking and bounding-box based perturbations.

Table 1. Representative perturbation-based XAI methods for object detection.

Among these, D-RISE is particularly appealing because it is fully model-agnostic and jointly considers classification and localisation via a similarity mea-

sure combining intersection-over-union (IoU), class probabilities, and objectness scores. However, D-RISE has several critical limitations that motivate our work.

2.3 Evaluating Saliency Maps

Visual inspection of saliency maps can be misleading: many heatmaps appear plausible even when they are uninformative or unrelated to the model’s decision. To rigorously assess saliency quality, several complementary evaluation criteria have been proposed.

Sanity checks. Sanity checks [1] test whether a saliency method truly depends on the learned model. Following the weight-randomisation procedure, one gradually replaces trained weights with random weights layer-by-layer. A faithful method should produce saliency maps that degrade as the model is randomised. If maps remain similar, the method may capture only input statistics.

Localization metrics. When pixel-level ground-truth annotations are available as segmentation masks, saliency maps can be evaluated by how well they overlap with the true object regions. A popular metric is the *pointing game* [18], where one checks whether the point of maximum saliency lies inside the ground-truth mask. The accuracy of this procedure over objects provides a simple localisation quality measure.

Fidelity metrics. Deletion and insertion metrics [9] evaluate how closely saliency aligns with the model’s decision process. In the deletion test, one starts from the original image and progressively masks pixels in decreasing saliency order, tracking the prediction score; a good explanation yields a rapid drop. In the insertion test, one starts from a blurred image and gradually reveals the most salient pixels; a good explanation produces a rapid increase in score. The area under the corresponding curves summarises fidelity.

For object detection, these evaluation tools must be adapted to per-detection saliency maps and detection-specific scores (e.g., class confidence or detection loss).

3 Background: D-RISE and Saliency Evaluation

3.1 Base Method: D-RISE

Let f be an object detector that, given an input image I , produces a set of detections $\{d_t\}_{t=1}^T$, where T denotes the number of detections produced for the image (see Figure 1 for an overview of the D-RISE workflow). Each detection d_t comprises a bounding box b_t , a class probability vector p_t , and an objectness score o_t .

D-RISE generates a collection of N random binary masks $\{M_i\}_{i=1}^N$, sampled at a given resolution and upsampled to the image size. For a fixed target detection

d_t in the original image, D-RISE computes a similarity score $s(d_t, d_{ij})$ between d_t and each detection d_{ij} produced on masked image i (usually based on IoU, class score, and objectness). The mask weight w_i is then obtained by taking the maximum similarity over all detections on that masked image. The final saliency map H_t for detection t is the weighted sum of the masks:

$$H_t = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i M_i. \quad (1)$$

After normalisation, H_t highlights pixels that, when kept unmasked, are most influential for target detection.

Fig. 1. Overview of the D-RISE pipeline used as the baseline in our study. Random binary masks are applied to the input image, the detector is run on each masked image, and similarity scores between the masked detections and the base detection are used as weights to aggregate the masks into a per-detection saliency map.

3.2 Limitations of D-RISE

While D-RISE provides useful qualitative insights for explaining object detector predictions, it suffers from several drawbacks which justify the need for a more task-aligned explainability score.

1. **Sensitivity to parameters.** The produced saliency maps strongly depend on the number of masks N , the mask resolution, the sampling probability p (fraction of unmasked area) and the upsampling method. Different parameter choices lead to markedly different explanations, without a leading way to select them for unseen inputs.
2. **Lack of negative attribution.** D-RISE only highlights regions positively contributing to a detection. It cannot identify pixels whose presence suppresses a correct detection or encourages a false one.
3. **No absolute importance.** The similarity-based weighting yields relative importance values but does not translate them into a quantitative, loss-related score.
4. **Limited practical usability.** The need for manual parameter tuning, combined with the absence of robustness guarantees, may limit replicability and consistency across different datasets and operating conditions.

These limitations reflect a broader challenge in the literature: the absence of a standardised explainability score explicitly tailored to object detection, limited robustness analysis across methods, and the lack of a widely adopted evaluation protocol that directly links saliency quality to detection performance.

4 Detection-Loss Based Explainability

4.1 Detection Loss

We now introduce a detection-specific loss function that combines classification and localisation terms. For a given detection, we define

$$L_{\text{det}} = L_{\text{cls}} + L_{\text{loc}}, \quad (2)$$

where:

$$L_{\text{cls}} = -\log p_{\text{class}}, \quad (3)$$

$$L_{\text{loc}} = 1 - \text{IoU}(b_{\text{base}}, b_{\text{masked}}). \quad (4)$$

Here, p_{class} is the predicted probability associated with the target class, and IoU is the intersection-over-union between the bounding box predicted on the original image (b_{base}) and the box predicted on the masked image (b_{masked}). This formulation penalises both misclassification and localisation errors, assigning larger loss to less accurate or less confident detections.

4.2 Importance as Performance Deterioration

Let $L_{\text{det}}^{\text{base}}$ denote the detection loss on the original image and $L_{\text{det}}^{(k)}$ the detection loss when the image is perturbed using mask M_k . We define the *raw* importance Δ_k associated with mask M_k as

$$\Delta_k = \max\left(0, L_{\text{det}}^{(k)} - L_{\text{det}}^{\text{base}}\right). \quad (5)$$

This quantity captures how much applying mask M_k degrades detection. If masking yields no additional loss (or even improves it), the importance is set to zero. If detection disappears or is severely degraded, Δ_k can become large, up to approximately $-\log(\varepsilon)$, where ε is a small probability reflecting complete loss of confidence.

This formulation has several advantages over the heuristic similarity measure used in D-RISE:

- it has a direct and intuitive interpretation: *importance equals performance drop*;
- it simultaneously penalises classification and localisation deterioration;
- it detects the case where the target object vanishes under masking;
- it naturally supports robustness analysis by examining how importance changes with masking parameters.

4.3 Normalized Explainability Score

To make importance values comparable across pixels, masks, and images, we normalise the raw scores. Given a collection of raw scores $\{\Delta_k\}$, we define the normalised importance

$$\Delta_k^{\text{norm}} = \frac{\Delta_k}{\max_j \Delta_j}, \quad (6)$$

so that $\Delta_k^{\text{norm}} \in [0, 1]$ for all k . Pixels with $\Delta_k^{\text{norm}} = 1$ are critical for the detection, while those with $\Delta_k^{\text{norm}} = 0$ have negligible impact.

In practice, we follow the D-RISE framework and generate N random masks $\{M_i\}$, computing the corresponding Δ_i values. The saliency map H for a detection is then obtained as

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta_i^{\text{norm}} M_i, \quad (7)$$

followed by normalisation to $[0, 1]$. This yields a per-pixel saliency map whose intensities directly reflect detection-loss deterioration.

4.4 From Local to Global Explainability

The detection-loss based score can be aggregated at different levels:

- **Object level:** per-detection saliency maps and summary statistics (e.g., mean or max importance over the object region).

- **Image level:** average explainability scores over all detections in an image, enabling comparison across images.
- **Model level:** distribution of explainability scores across a dataset, enabling comparison between detectors or training configurations.

This kind of aggregation allows to quantify not only “where” each detection looks, but also “how explainable” a model is on a given dataset.

5 Experimental Design

This section describes the detectors and datasets used in our study, the evaluation metrics for both accuracy and explainability and the analysis of the generated saliency maps.

5.1 Models and Datasets

Experiments are conducted on three datasets: the large-scale public COCO benchmark [6] and two application-driven industrial datasets, specifically a screw detection dataset and a screen and frame detection dataset [3]. Both industrial datasets were jointly developed within the RoboSAPIENS project [5] and are publicly available.

This combination allows to evaluate explainability methods under complementary conditions, ranging from generic object detection in unconstrained environments to fine-grained detection in robotic manipulation scenarios. Both D-RISE and the proposed detection-loss Δ -based method are applied consistently across all datasets.

COCO dataset The Common Objects in Context (COCO) dataset is a standard benchmark for object detection, containing more than 200,000 annotated images across 80 object categories. It features complex scenes with clutter, occlusions, and strong appearance variability.

Screw detection dataset This dataset addresses an industrial robotic disassembly scenario where a robot arm, equipped with a camera and a screwdriver, detects and removes screws from a computer. It consists of 2,997 images (1,005 original and 1,992 augmented) at 1280×720 resolution, with 490 validation images. Data augmentation includes rotation, flipping, cropping, blur, and exposure changes. Images are annotated using Roboflow.

Screen and frame detection dataset This dataset targets the detection of a computer screen and its surrounding frame during automated disassembly. It contains 342 images (160 original and 182 augmented), with 46 validation images, at 1280×720 resolution. The same augmentation and annotation pipeline as in the screw detection dataset is used.

5.2 Detection Performance

Detection performance is evaluated using standard object detection metrics, including mAP at multiple IoU thresholds, as well as precision and recall. All models achieve stable detection accuracy across datasets, ensuring that explainability analyses are conducted on detectors with meaningful predictive performance. As the focus of this work is on explainability rather than detection accuracy, for sake of brevity detailed numerical results are not reported in this article.

5.3 Explainability Analysis

We compare D-RISE and the proposed detection-loss Δ -based method on all three datasets by analysing the resulting saliency maps and their alignment with the corresponding detections. Saliency maps are generated independently for each detected object and overlaid on the input image together with the corresponding bounding boxes.

Industrial datasets. We begin with the industrial datasets, where explainability is particularly important due to the safety-critical nature of robotic manipulation tasks. Figures 2 and 3 show example images from the screw detection and screen and frame detection datasets along with the corresponding YOLO detections. These detections serve as the reference outputs for the saliency analysis presented in Figures 4 and 5.

Fig. 2. Example image from the screw detection dataset with YOLO detections. The detector identifies two objects (“holder” and “noscrew”), which form the basis for evaluating the D-RISE and detection-loss based saliency methods.

Fig. 3. Example image from the screen and frame detection dataset with YOLO detections. The detector identifies two objects (“screen” and “screen.frame”), which form the basis for evaluating the D-RISE and detection-loss based saliency methods.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the proposed detection-loss based saliency maps and D-RISE on the screw-detection dataset.

On the screw detection dataset (Fig. 4), both D-RISE and the proposed Δ -based method produce highly localised saliency maps concentrated on the detected object regions. When using identical masking parameters, the qualitative differences between the two approaches are limited, and both methods provide coherent explanations aligned with the predicted bounding boxes.

On the screen and frame detection dataset (Fig. 5), both D-RISE and the proposed Δ -based method highlight regions within the predicted bounding boxes. For the *screen* class, saliency is mainly concentrated on the display surface in

Fig. 5. Comparison between the proposed detection-loss based saliency maps and D-RISE on the screen and frame detection dataset.

both approaches. For the *screen_frame* class, the highlighted regions follow some parts of the frame structure.

Qualitatively, the two methods produce comparable explanations under the same masking parameters. D-RISE tends to produce slightly broader activation patterns, while the Δ -based method yields somewhat more compact saliency in some cases. However, in this controlled industrial setting, the overall qualitative differences between the two methods remain moderate, and both provide visually plausible explanations.

COCO dataset. Compared to the industrial datasets, differences between D-RISE and the proposed Δ -based method on COCO are less pronounced. In the example shown in Figure 6, both approaches generate saliency maps that are largely aligned with the detected objects, with high responses located inside the corresponding bounding boxes.

For the *truck* detection, both methods highlight visually distinctive regions of the vehicle, while for the two *person* detections, saliency is primarily concentrated on the upper body and head regions. In this natural and visually complex scene, both approaches yield coherent and visually plausible explanations without evident failure cases.

These observations suggest that, on generic object detection tasks such as in COCO dataset, the relative behaviour of D-RISE and the proposed Δ -based method can depend on the specific image and scene composition. While both ap-

(a) D-RISE (truck)

(b) D-RISE (person 1)

(c) D-RISE (person 2)

(d) Δ -based (truck)

(e) Δ -based (person 1)

(f) Δ -based (person 2)

Fig. 6. Comparison of D-RISE and detection-loss based saliency maps on COCO. The original input image is shown on top for reference.

proaches may produce similarly interpretable explanations in certain cases, they rely on fundamentally different principles: D-RISE estimates pixel importance through random masking and score aggregation, whereas the proposed method directly measures the impact of input perturbations on the detection loss.

In addition to qualitative inspection, we report object-level quantitative measures for the proposed Δ -based method. Specifically, we evaluate: (i) the concentration of saliency inside the predicted bounding box, summarised by the mean and maximum importance values as well as the Importance Overlap (IO) ratio, which is computed as the fraction of total saliency mass inside the predicted bounding box; and (ii) deletion fidelity, where the most salient pixels inside the predicted bounding box are progressively removed and the corresponding decrease in detection confidence is measured.

Table 2. Object-level explainability statistics and deletion AUC scores for the proposed Δ -based method across three datasets. Mean and maximum importance summarise saliency intensity within each detection, IO ratio measures the concentration of saliency inside the predicted bounding box, and deletion AUC quantifies the sensitivity of detection confidence under progressive removal of salient pixels.

Dataset	Object	Mean Imp.	Max Imp.	IO Ratio	Del. AUC
Frame/Screen	Screen	0.569	1.000	0.328	0.152
Frame/Screen	Screen Frame	0.550	1.000	0.454	0.331
Screw	Holder	0.533	1.000	0.015	0.385
Screw	Non Screw	0.934	0.996	0.003	0.159
COCO	Truck	0.333	1.000	0.461	0.230
COCO	Person 1	0.333	1.000	0.084	0.032
COCO	Person 2	0.446	1.000	0.059	0.058

Table 2 provides quantitative support for the qualitative observations. Across datasets, saliency values are generally concentrated within the predicted object regions, with larger objects (e.g., screen frame and truck) exhibiting comparatively higher IO ratios. For instance, COCO truck detection achieves an IO ratio of 0.461 and a deletion AUC of 0.230, indicating that removal of highly ranked pixels leads to a measurable reduction in detection confidence. Similarly, screen-frame detection in the industrial dataset shows both a relatively high IO ratio (0.454) and deletion AUC (0.331), confirming that the highlighted regions align with features critical for correct prediction.

Lower IO ratios observed for smaller objects (e.g., screws and persons) are consistent with the increased difficulty of concentrating saliency on fine-grained regions embedded in larger image contexts.

Nevertheless, deletion AUC values indicate that removing the most salient pixels consistently leads to a reduction in detection confidence.

5.4 Summary

Across all evaluated datasets, the proposed detection-loss based explainability method produces saliency maps coherent with the detector’s prediction objective. By defining importance in terms of detection-loss deterioration, the Δ -based formulation explicitly links explanation scores to both classification confidence and localisation quality.

Qualitative results demonstrate that the generated saliency maps highlight semantically meaningful regions in both industrial and natural-image scenarios. Object-level statistics further indicate that importance values tend to concentrate within predicted bounding boxes, particularly for larger objects. Indeed, deletion experiments confirm the functional relevance of these regions: progressively removing highly ranked pixels consistently leads to measurable reductions in detection confidence.

While quantitative values vary with object scale and scene complexity, the method exhibits stable behaviour across different domains, ranging from fine-grained industrial components to complex natural scenes. Overall, the results support the effectiveness of the proposed detection-loss based framework as a performance-aligned and interpretable approach for explaining object detection models.

6 Discussion and Future Work

The detection-loss based explainability score proposed in this work transforms perturbation outputs into a quantitative measure of importance directly aligned with object detection performance. The score addresses several limitations of heuristic similarity-based approaches directly measuring performance deterioration under masking:

- it links saliency intensity to both classification confidence and localisation quality;
- it yields normalised importance values in $[0, 1]$, easing interpretation and comparison;
- it extends to robustness analysis and model comparison across detections, and potential aggregation at the dataset level.

The empirical results show as the method produces spatially coherent explanations. Object-level statistics quantify how concentrated saliency stays within predicted bounding boxes, while deletion analysis provides a functional evaluation of explanation sensitivity. Even if deletion AUC values vary depending on object size and scene complexity, the results consistently depict that highlighted regions influence detection confidence in a measurable manner.

Beyond visual interpretability, this framework can be integrated into industrial practices. In applications such as autonomous driving or industrial inspection, operators may use the proposed saliency maps to verify whether the detector focuses on semantically meaningful regions. The normalised explainability

scores additionally provide a compact numerical summary of detection reliance on specific image areas, supporting auditing and validation processes.

Future work may be focused on a comprehensive empirical evaluation across multiple detectors (e.g., different YOLO variants, two-stage detectors) and datasets, as well as on:

- extending the score to account for negative attribution, i.e., regions whose presence harms correct detections;
- integrating detection-loss based saliency into active learning and dataset curation pipelines;
- combining our perturbation-based approach with gradient-based signals to reduce computational cost while preserving fidelity.

7 Conclusions

This work introduced a detection-loss based explainability framework for object detection. By defining saliency in terms of performance deterioration under structured masking perturbations, the proposed Δ -based formulation aligns explanation scoring with the detector’s classification and localisation objectives.

Qualitative analysis across multiple datasets demonstrates spatially-meaningful saliency behaviour, while object-level statistics and deletion-based evaluation provide quantitative evidence that highlighted regions influence detection confidence. The normalisation and task-aligned formulation of the score enable interpretation and comparison across object categories and datasets.

Overall, the proposed framework contributes towards addressing several open challenges in explainable object detection, including the lack of numeric explainability scores and the limited connection between explanations and detection accuracy. It provides a step toward more standardised and quantitative comparison of XAI methods in detection tasks and contributes to the development of safer and more trustworthy object detection systems.

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9 Author Contributions

Rasha Zieni conducted the research, the coding and the data analysis, and prepared the manuscript. François Picard conceived the study and provided the

data. Walter Quadrini contributed through hosting, discussion and proofreading. Leila Belmerhnia and Georgios Spathoulas contributed through discussion. Paolo Giudici proposed the methodology and provided supervision.

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